

Estimation of Overlapping Coefficients Using the Fourth- Order Kernel Method

Thesis for Master Degree of Statistics

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Abstract

The overlapping coefficient is defined as the common area under two distributions. Most of overlapping studies used the parametric method, which assumes that the two distributions are known (the data have specific parametric models) with unknown parameters. It is not easy job to verify that the assumptions of model are valid to give good estimators. The nonparametric method is an important tool to estimate the required model directly from the data itself. The most well known nonparametric method is the kernel method, which is an effective tool for estimating the model especially where parametric model is found to be inappropriate or difficult to specify. The latest study by Al-Talafha (2016) shows that the kernel method is a very useful technique to estimate the overlapping coefficients. The nonparametric fourth-order kernel is another adaptation of the classical kernel method with asymptotic properties better than that of the classical kernel. Therefore, we expect that the fourth-order kernel method produces better estimators for the overlapping coefficients. In this thesis, the fourth-order kernel method is considered to estimate the three overlapping coefficients, Morisita measure λ , Matusita measure ρ and Weitzman measure Δ . The method produces at least two new estimators for each measure and the performances of the resulting estimators are investigated and compared with the classical kernel estimators via simulation technique. The results show that the fourth-order kernel estimators are very acceptable and in many considered cases, their performances are better than that of the classical kernel estimator.

Key words: Overlapping coefficient, Fourth order kernel, Classical kernel, Parametric method, Relative bias, Efficiency, Kernel function, Smoothing parameter.

المخلص

يعرف معامل التداخل على أنه المساحة المشتركة تحت توزيعين احتماليين. معظم الدراسات استخدمت الأسلوب المعلمي لتقدير معاملات التداخل، وهذا الأسلوب يفترض أن التوزيعين معروفان (البيانات ذات نماذج معيارية محددة) مع معلمات غير معروفة. ليس من السهل التحقق فيما إذا كانت افتراضات النموذج للبيانات صحيحة أو لا وذلك للحصول على تقديرات جيدة. الطريقة غير المعلمية هي أداة هامة لتقدير النموذج المطلوب مباشرة من البيانات نفسها. والطريقة الغير معلمية الأكثر شهرة هي طريقة النواة، وهي أداة فعالة لتقدير النموذج خاصة عندما يكون النموذج المعلمي غير ملائم أو يصعب تحديده. أظهرت الدراسة الأخيرة التي أجراها طلافحة (2016) أن أسلوب النواة الكلاسيكي (من الدرجة الثانية) هو أسلوب مفيد جدا لتقدير معاملات التداخل. طريقة النواة من الدرجة الرابعة هي أسلوب اخر مشتق من الطريقة الكلاسيكية ولها خصائص رياضية أفضل من تلك الخصائص المناظرة لطريقة النواة الكلاسيكية وذلك لاجام العينات الكبيرة. في هذه الأطروحة، تم التركيز على طريقة النواة من الدرجة الرابعة وذلك لتقدير لمعاملات التداخل الثلاثة وهي، مقياس موريسينا λ ، مقياس ماتوسينا ρ و مقياس ويتزمان Δ . باستخدام الطريقة المقترحة تم اشتقاق مقدرين على الاقل لكل مقياس وتم دراسة أداء المقدرات الناتجة ومقارنتها مع مقدر النواة الكلاسيكي عن طريق تقنية المحاكاة. أظهرت النتائج أن مقدر النواة من الدرجة الرابعة مقبول جدا وفي العديد من الحالات الماخوذة قيد الدرس فإن أدائها كان أفضل من مقدر النواة الكلاسيكي.

الكلمات الرئيسية: معاملات التداخل ، مقدر النواة اللامعلمي من الدرجة الرابعة ، مقدر النواة اللامعلمي من الدرجة الثانية (الكلاسيكي)، الطريقة المعلمية، قيم التحيز النسبية، الكفاءة، اقتران النواة ، تمهيد المعلمة.

CHAPTER ONE

Introduction and Literature Review

1.1 Introduction

There are three measures for overlapping coefficient (OVL), namely Matusita measure ρ , Morisita measure λ and Weitzman measure Δ . The Weitzman's measure Δ is widely used and simply explained. It is defined to be the area under two probability density functions simultaneously or it refers to be the intersected area by the graphs of two probability density functions. Computing the overlapping coefficient between two densities gives an idea about the degree of similarity, agreement or closeness of two phenomenons whose elements follow the given densities.

Let $f_1(x)$ and $f_2(x)$ be two continuous probability density functions, then the OVL is defined by one of the following three measures ρ , λ or Δ .

1) Matusita measure (1955):

$$\rho = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{f_1(x)f_2(x)} dx$$

1) Morisita measure (1959):

$$\lambda = \frac{2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_1(x) f_2(x) dx}{\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [f_1(x)]^2 + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [f_2(x)]^2} dx$$

2) Weitzman measure (1970):

$$\Delta = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{f_1(x), f_2(x)\} dx$$

These measures can be directly applied to discrete distributions by replacing the integrals with summations.

The value of each of the above measures is ranging from 0 to 1. If the OVL value is 0 then it indicates that the two populations are entirely different and there is no common area between two densities. If the OVL value is 1 then it indicates a perfect agreement between the two population densities.

1.2 Examples and graphs for OVL Δ

The Weitzman's measure Δ for four examples are computed and plotted in this section. Let X and Y be two independent random variables, where $X \sim f_1(x, \theta_1, \theta_2)$ and $Y \sim f_2(x, \theta_3, \theta_4)$. Also, let $N(\theta_1, \theta_2)$ denotes the normal distribution with mean θ_1 and variance θ_2 and let $Wei(\theta_1, \theta_2)$ denotes the Weibull distribution with scale parameter θ_1 and shape parameter θ_2 , where the probability density of weibull distribution is

$$f(x) = \frac{\theta_2}{\theta_1} \left(\frac{x}{\theta_1}\right)^{\theta_2-1} e^{-\left(\frac{x}{\theta_1}\right)^{\theta_2}}, \quad x > 0.$$

We will compute the exact value of Δ for each of the following four cases. Also, the shaded area that represents Δ for each case are given in Figures (1.1 - 1.4).

Case (I): Let $f_1(x, \theta_1, \theta_2) = N(11, 1)$ and $f_2(y, \theta_3, \theta_4) = N(13, 1)$.

The shaded area in Figure (1.1) represents the measure Δ . The exact value of Δ can be computed as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{N(11, 1), N(13, 1)\} dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^c N(13, 1) dx + \int_c^{\infty} N(11, 1) dx,\end{aligned}$$

Where c is the intersection point between the curve of $N(11, 1)$ and that of $N(13, 1)$, which equal to 12. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= \int_{-\infty}^{-1} N(0, 1) dx + \int_1^{\infty} N(0, 1) dx, \\ &= 2 \int_{-\infty}^{-1} N(0, 1) dx \\ &= 2 (0.1587) \\ &= 0.3174.\end{aligned}$$

Case (II): $f_1(x, \theta_1, \theta_2) = N(11, 1)$ and $f_2(y, \theta_3, \theta_4) = N(11, 4)$,

The intersection points between the two curves of $N(11, 1)$ and $N(11, 4)$ are 9.64044 and 12.3596 respectively (see figure 1.2).

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min \{N(11, 1), N(11, 4)\} dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{9.64044} N(11, 1) dx + \int_{9.64044}^{12.3596} N(11, 4) dx + \int_{12.3596}^{\infty} N(11, 1) dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{-1.35956} N(0, 1) dx + \int_{-0.67978}^{0.67978} N(0, 1) dx + \int_{1.3596}^{\infty} N(0, 1) dx\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= 0.0869 + 0.7517 - 0.2483 + 0.086 \\
&= 0.6772.
\end{aligned}$$

Figures (1.3) and (1.4) represent the following two cases, respectively:

Case (III): $f_1(x, \theta_1, \theta_2) = N(10, 2.2)$ and $f_2(y, \theta_3, \theta_4) = N(11, 1.2)$

(see Figure 1.3) and

Case (IV): $f_1(x, \theta_1, \theta_2) = Wei(3, 1.5)$ and $f_2(y, \theta_3, \theta_4) = N(4, 1)$

(see Figure 1.4).

The exact values of Δ for the above two cases can be computed similarly to Case (I) and Case (II).

Figure (1.1). The shaded area is the value of Δ for $N(11, 1)$ and $N(13, 1)$. The exact value of $\Delta = 0.3174$.

Figure (1.2). The shaded area is the value of Δ for $N(11,1)$ and $N(11,4)$. The exact value of $\Delta = 0.6772$.

Figure (1.3). The shaded area is the value of Δ for $N(10,2.2)$ and $N(11,1.2)$. The exact value of $\Delta = 0.6780$.

Figure (1.4). The shaded area is the value of Δ for $Wei(3, 1.5)$ and $N(4, 1)$. The exact value of $\Delta = 0.4836$.

1.3 Estimation of OVL coefficients and literature review

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1} and Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_{n_2} be two independent random samples from $f_X(x, \theta_1)$ and $f_Y(x, \theta_2)$ respectively, where θ_1 and θ_2 are two parameters such that each of them may be a vector. Estimation of the three OVL ρ , λ and Δ are mainly investigated by using parametric or nonparametric methods. On one hand, the parametric method assumes that the probability density functions $f_X(x, \theta_1)$ and $f_Y(x, \theta_2)$ are known with unknown parameters θ_1 and θ_2 , which can be estimated by the classical estimation methods, like the method of moments (MM) or the maximum likelihood (ML) method. On the other hand, the nonparametric method requires no assumptions about the functional form of the density function. The nonparametric density estimation method allows the data at

hand to talk about themselves and determines the shape of their probability density function.

1.3.1 Parametric method

Inman and Bradly (1989) derived the MLE of Δ under the assumption that the two densities are normal with different means and equal variances (e.g. see Figure 1.1). Mulekar and Mishra (1994) studied the OVL of two normal densities in the case of equal means but different variances (e.g. see Figure 1.2). Also, under the assumption that the two densities are normal with equal means, Mulekar and Mishra (2000) compared the confidence intervals for the overlapping coefficients ρ , λ and Δ computed using re-sampling technique, namely, Jackknife, bootstrap and transformation methods. Reiser and Faraggi (1999) constructed generalized confidence intervals for the OVL of two normal distributions with equal variance. Madhuri *et al.* (2001) and Al-Saleh and Samawi (2007) investigated the three OVL for two exponential populations with different scale parameters. Al-Saidy *et al.* (2005) considered the three OVL for two Weibull distributions having the same shape parameter and different scale parameters. Samawi and Al-Saleh (2008) used the ranked set sampling method to draw inference about the three OVL ρ , λ and Δ in the case of two exponential distributions with different scale parameters. Also they constructed confident intervals for the OVL using bootstrap and Taylor series methods. Helu and Samawi (2011) studied the

effect of sampling procedures on the OVL by comparing the simple random sampling technique with the ranked set sampling technique when the original data are assumed to follow the Lomax models.

When the true distribution for a given data set is close to the assumed parametric density then parametric method performs well (see Al-Talafha, 2016). However, it is not always an easy job to verify the validity of model assumption and unsuitable models may lead to poor performances of the parametric method. When one has some doubt about the validity of model assumptions, it is always safe to use nonparametric method, which do not require any assumption about the form of the data density.

1.3.2 Nonparametric method

Nonparametric method to estimate the OVL coefficient can be used to estimate the probability densities themselves. The estimated densities are then substituted by the formula of the corresponding coefficient to evaluate its integral. Clemons and Bradley (2000) and Clemons (2001) used the classical kernel method to estimate the Weitzman's measure Δ . Their method is described with several steps using available computer programs in FORTRAN. Mizuno *et al.* (2005) used the OVL Δ to assess the similarity of pharmacokinetic data between ethnically different populations. They used the nonparametric kernel method to make an

inference about Δ . Ridout and Linkie (2008) used Δ to measure the similarity between two activity patterns. They estimated the measure Δ nonparametrically by using the kernel method. Samawi *et al.* (2011) introduced the nonparametric kernel method to estimate Δ in order to perform a test about the symmetry of the underlying distribution of the study population. Schmid and Schmidt (2006) suggested some nonparametric estimators for Δ using an empirical application about income of men and women in Germany to compare between East Germany and West Germany. . Finally, Martens *et al.* (2014) used kernel method to estimate Δ in order to measure the similarity of distributions between treatment groups in propensity scores method.

The above nonparametric kernel method is used to estimate the Weitzman's measure Δ only. None of them is used to estimate the other two OVL measures ρ and λ . In his master thesis, Al-Talafha (2016) used the classical kernel method to estimate the three measures ρ , λ and Δ .

1.3 Classical kernel method

Let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be a random sample of size n from a continuous distribution $f(x)$, where $x \in R$, then the nonparametric classical kernel estimator $\hat{f}_k(x)$ of $f(x)$ is (Silverman, 1986)

$$\hat{f}_k(x) = \frac{1}{nb} \sum_{i=1}^n K\left(\frac{x-X_i}{b}\right), \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (1.1)$$

Where b is called a smoothing parameter (or a bandwidth) and K is called a second-order kernel function assumed to be symmetric and satisfies

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(t)dt = 1, \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} tK(t)dt = 0, \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^2K(t)dt = s_2 \neq 0.$$

Under the assumptions that $b \rightarrow 0$ and $nb \rightarrow \infty$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$, the bias and variance of $\hat{f}_k(x)$ are (Silverman, 1986 and Wand and Jones, 1995)

$$\text{Bias}(\hat{f}_k(x)) = b^2 f''(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^2 K(t)dt + o(b^2)$$

and

$$\text{Var}(\hat{f}_k(x)) = \frac{f(x)}{nb} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(t)^2 dt + o(n^{-1}b^{-1})$$

where $f''(x)$ is the second derivative of $f(x)$.

Note that the convergence rate of the bias and variance of $\hat{f}_k(x)$ are $O(b^2)$ and $O(n^{-1}b^{-1})$ respectively.

1.5 Fourth-order kernel method

The nonparametric fourth-order kernel estimator $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$ of $f(x)$ is (Wand and Jones, 1995)

$$\hat{f}_{fo}(x) = \frac{1}{nh} \sum_{i=1}^n K_{(4)}\left(\frac{x-X_i}{h}\right), \quad -\infty < x < \infty \quad (1.2)$$

The function $K_{(4)}(u)$ is called a fourth-order kernel function and is given by

$$K_{(4)}(t) = \frac{(s_4 - s_2 t^2) K(t)}{s_4 - s_2^2},$$

where $s_j = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^j K(u) du$. If $K(t)$ is a standard normal distribution, then $s_2 = 1$ and $s_4 = 3$. In this case,

$$\begin{aligned} K_{(4)}(t) &= \frac{3 - t^2}{2} K(t) \\ &= \frac{3 - t^2}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-t^2/2} \end{aligned}$$

Under the assumptions $h \rightarrow 0$ and $nh \rightarrow \infty$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$, the bias and variance of $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$ are

$$\text{Bias}(\hat{f}_{fo}(x)) = \frac{h^4}{4!} f^{(4)}(x) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^4 K_{(4)}(t) dt + o(h^4)$$

and

$$\text{Var}(\hat{f}_{fo}(x)) = \frac{f(x)}{nh} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K_{(4)}(t)^2 dt + o(n^{-1}h^{-1}),$$

where $f^{(4)}(x)$ is the fourth derivative of $f(x)$. The convergence rate of bias and variance of $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$ are $O(h^4)$ and $O(n^{-1}h^{-1})$ respectively. By comparing the biases and variances of the two estimators $\hat{f}_k(x)$ and $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$, it is clear that the convergence rate for the variances of the two

estimators are equal, while the bias convergence rate is $O(h^4)$ for $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$ and $O(b^2)$ for $\hat{f}_k(x)$. This means that bias of $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$ tends to zero faster than that of $\hat{f}_k(x)$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$.

Under the assumptions $h \rightarrow 0$ and $nh \rightarrow \infty$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$, Eidous and Al-Masri (2010) derived the asymptotic properties of $\hat{f}_{fo}(0)$ using line transect data. They also showed that the estimator $\hat{f}_{fo}(0)$ performs better than $\hat{f}_k(0)$ for finite sample sizes.

1.6 Kernel function

The kernel function, K that used in nonparametric kernel estimator (1.1) and fourth-order kernel estimator (1.2) need to be determined. All functions that satisfy $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} K(t)dt = 1$, $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} tK(t)dt = 0$ and $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^2K(t)dt = s_2 \neq 0$ can be used as a kernel function (Silverman, 1986). The following kernel functions are candidate for this purpose:

1) Uniform kernel:

$$K(u) = \frac{1}{2}I_{\{|u| \leq 1\}}.$$

2) Triangle kernel:

$$K(u) = (1 - |u|)I_{\{|u| \leq 1\}}.$$

3) Epanechnikov kernel:

$$K(u) = \frac{3}{4}(1 - u^2)I_{\{|u| \leq 1\}}.$$

4) Quadratic (biweight) kernel:

$$K(u) = \frac{15}{16}(1 - u^2)^2I_{\{|u| \leq 1\}}.$$

5) Gaussian kernel:

$$K(u) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}e^{-\frac{1}{2}u^2},$$

where $I_{\{|u| \leq 1\}} = \begin{cases} 1, & |u| \leq 1 \\ 0, & o.w \end{cases}$. Silverman (1986) showed that there is a very little lost efficiency of the kernel estimator $\hat{f}_k(x)$ by adopting any one of the above kernel functions. They all performed similarly on the basis of the asymptotic mean integrated square error of $\hat{f}_k(x)$. In this thesis, we chose to use the Gaussian kernel function.

1.7 Smoothing parameter

The determination value of the smoothing parameter b in Equation (1.1) and h in Equation (1.2) is an important issue in nonparametric density estimation. It plays a vital role in the performance of the classical kernel estimator $\hat{f}_k(x)$ (Silverman, 1986) or the performance of fourth-order kernel estimator $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$ (Wand and Jones, 1995). The common method to determine the smoothing parameter of $\hat{f}_k(x)$ or $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$ is by minimizing

the corresponding asymptotic mean integral square error (*MISE*) of that estimator. The *MISE* of $\hat{f}_k(x)$ is defined by (Silverman, 1986)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{MISE}(\hat{f}_k(x)) &= \int E \left(\hat{f}(x) - f(x) \right)^2 dx \\ &= \int \text{MSE} \left(\hat{f}(x) \right) dx \\ &= \int \text{bias}^2 \left(\hat{f}_k(x) \right) dx + \int \text{var} \left(\hat{f}(x) \right) dx \end{aligned}$$

Let $M(K) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (K(t))^2 dt$, $R_j = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f^{(j)^2}(x) dx$ and $r_j(K) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} t^j K(t) dt$, then the asymptotic *MISE* of $\hat{f}_k(x)$ is

$$\text{AMISE} \left(\hat{f}_k(x) \right) = b^4 r_2^2(K) R_2 + \frac{M(K)}{nb}.$$

By considering $\text{MISE}(\hat{f}_k(x))$ as a function of b (say $s(b)$) and by taking the first derivative of $s(b)$ with respect to b and equating it to zero, we obtain

$$b = \left(\frac{M(k)}{4r_2^2(k)R_2} \right)^{1/5} n^{-1/5},$$

which is the formula of b that minimize the asymptotic $\text{MISE}(\hat{f}_k(x))$. In the same way, we can obtain the formula of h that minimizes the asymptotic *MISE* of $\hat{f}_{fo}(x)$, which is given by

$$h = \left(\frac{81 M(k_{(4)})}{r_4^2(k_{(4)}) R_4} \right)^{1/9} n^{-1/9} .$$

If the kernel function is taken to be the Gaussian function, i.e. $K(t) = N(0,1)$ and if $f(x)$ is assumed to be $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$ then

$$b = 1.06 \sigma n^{-1/5}$$

and

$$h = 1.0067 \sigma n^{-1/9} ,$$

where σ can be estimated by its maximum likelihood estimator, which is

given by $\hat{\sigma} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n}}$. Instead of using $\hat{\sigma}$ as estimator for σ , silverman

(1986) proposed to estimate σ by

$$A = \min\{\text{standard deviation, interquartile range} / 1.34\}$$

In this case, the formula of b can be estimated by

$$b = 1.06 A n^{-1/5} \tag{1.3}$$

and the formula of h by

$$h = 1.006 A n^{-1/9} \tag{1.4}$$

The simulation results of Chapter (4) of this thesis are computed using the above formulas (1.3) and (1.4).

The nonparametric density estimation methods were used in various area included the estimation of population abundance. Early foundational work by Eidous (2004a, 2004b) introduced histogram and kernel-based techniques to improve density estimation. In subsequent years, a wide range of methods evolved, including polygon and bias-corrected histogram estimators (Eidous, 2005a, 2005c), and kernel enhancements (Eidous, 2005b, 2005d, 2006, 2009, 2011, 2012). More recent contributions focused on bias correction for kernel and double kernel approaches (Eidous and Shakhathreh, 2011, 2012).

1.8 Statement of the problem

Al-Talafha (2016) used the classical kernel method to estimate the three measures ρ , λ and Δ . He compared the resulting kernel estimators with their parametric counterparts. His results indicated that the parametric methods are very sensitive to model miss-specification. That is, unsuitable densities lead to very poor performances of parametric methods. Therefore, he reported that the nonparametric classical kernel method provides an automatic safeguard against possible deviations from parametric model assumptions.

As a nonparametric method, we suggest to use the fourth-order kernel method to estimate the different OVL measures. As discussed in Section 1.4 and 1.5, the asymptotic properties of the fourth-order kernel estimator

are better than those of the classical kernel estimator. Therefore, we expect that the using of the fourth-order kernel method, as an alternative to the classical kernel method can improve the nonparametric estimators of the different overlapping measures. More specifically, in this thesis:

- 1) We showed how we can apply the fourth-order kernel method in order to estimate the OVL measures ρ , λ and Δ .
- 2) We derived new nonparametric estimators for ρ , λ and Δ based on the fourth-order kernel method.
- 3) We compared the new fourth-order kernel estimators of ρ , λ and Δ with the corresponding classical kernel estimators by using the simulation technique.

1.9 Thesis organization

This thesis is divided into five chapters. Chapter one is an introduction about the overlapping measures and it gives some relevant material. In chapter two, we derived two new estimators for Morisita measure λ by using the fourth-order kernel method. In chapter three, we proposed and derived new fourth-order kernel estimators for the other two coefficients ρ and Δ . A simulation study and a numerical comparison between the classical kernel and fourth-order kernel methods are given in chapter

four. Chapter five gives the final conclusions and the suggestions for future work.

CHAPTER TWO

Fourth-Order Kernel Estimator for Morisita Measure λ

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we derived two new estimators for Morisita measure λ . The fourth-order kernel method is used for this purpose. The first estimator is derived by using directly the fourth-order kernel estimators of $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(x)$ in the formula of λ . The other estimator is obtained by using the method of moments technique.

2.2 Morisita measure and notations

Let X and Y be two independent random variables with pdf $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$. The Morisita overlapping measure λ can be defined as

$$\lambda = \frac{2\gamma_{XY}}{\gamma_X + \gamma_Y}$$

where

$$\gamma_{XY} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x) f_Y(x) dx$$

$$\gamma_{XX} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [f_X(x)]^2 dx$$

and

$$\gamma_{YY} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} [f_Y(x)]^2 dx$$

Now, let X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1} be a random sample from $f_X(x)$ and Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_{n_2} be another random sample from $f_Y(y)$, where the two samples are independent. The main objective of this chapter is to estimate λ based on these two random samples. The estimation of λ equivalents to estimate γ_{XY} , γ_{XX} and γ_{YY} .

2.3 Fourth-order kernel estimator of λ

As discussed in chapter one, the fourth-order kernel estimators of $f_X(x)$ based on a random sample X_1, X_2, \dots, X_{n_1} is

$$\hat{f}_X(x) = \frac{1}{n_1 h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} K_{(4)}\left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1}\right)$$

and the fourth-order kernel estimator of $f_Y(x)$ based on a random sample Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_{n_2} is

$$\hat{f}_Y(x) = \frac{1}{n_2 h_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} K_{(4)}\left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2}\right),$$

where the fourth-order kernel function $k_{(4)}(\cdot)$ in the above equations is given by

$$k_{(4)}(t) = \frac{3 - t^2}{2} K(t)$$

(see section 1.5). If the second order kernel function is taken to be Gaussian function, i.e $K(t) = N(0,1)$ then the fourth-order kernel function becomes

$$k_{(4)}(t) = \frac{3 - t^2}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{t^2}{2}}$$

By substituting $k_{(4)}(t)$ back into the formulas of $\hat{f}_X(x)$ and $\hat{f}_Y(x)$ we obtain,

$$\hat{f}_X(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2\pi}n_1h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \left(3 - \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2}$$

and,

$$\hat{f}_Y(x) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{2\pi}n_2h_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \left(3 - \left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2} \right)^2}$$

Now, we suggest to estimate γ_{XY} , γ_{XX} and γ_{YY} by $\hat{\gamma}_{XY}$, $\hat{\gamma}_{XX}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{YY}$ respectively, where

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XY} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{f}_X(x) \hat{f}_Y(x) dx$$

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XX} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\hat{f}_X(x) \right)^2 dx$$

and

$$\hat{\gamma}_{YY} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\hat{f}_Y(x))^2 dx.$$

So, the fourth-order kernel estimator of λ is

$$\hat{\lambda}_1 = 2 \frac{\hat{\gamma}_{XY}}{\hat{\gamma}_{XX} + \hat{\gamma}_{YY}} \quad (2.1)$$

2.3.1 Derivation of $\hat{\gamma}_{XY}$

To find $\hat{\gamma}_{XY} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{f}_X(x) \hat{f}_Y(x) dx$, we first consider the product of $\hat{f}_X(x)$ and $\hat{f}_Y(y)$, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_X(x) \hat{f}_Y(y) &= \frac{1}{8\pi n_1 n_2 h_1 h_2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \left(3 - \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2} \right) \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \left(3 - \left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2} \right)^2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi n_1 n_2 h_1 h_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \left[\left(9 - 3 \left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x - y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Now, by taking the integral of both sides of the above equation with respect to x , we obtain

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XY} = \frac{1}{8\pi n_1 n_2 h_1 h_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} \left[9 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx \right. \\ \left. - 3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx - 3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx \right. \\ \left. + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx \right].$$

To simplify the calculations, let

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XY} = \frac{1}{8\pi n_1 n_2 h_1 h_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} [9A - 3B - 3C + D]$$

where,

$$A = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx$$

$$B = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx$$

$$C = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx$$

and

$$D = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx.$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned}
A &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-y_j}{h_2} \right)^2 \right]} dx \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\frac{x_i^2}{h_1^2} + \frac{y_j^2}{h_2^2} \right]} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\frac{x^2}{h_1^2} + \frac{x^2}{h_2^2} - \frac{2x(h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j)}{h_1^2 h_2^2} \right]} dx \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\frac{x_i^2}{h_1^2} + \frac{y_j^2}{h_2^2} \right]} e^{\frac{h_1^2 + h_2^2}{2h_1^2 h_2^2} \left[x^2 - \frac{2x(h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]} dx \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\frac{x_i^2}{h_1^2} + \frac{y_j^2}{h_2^2} \right]} e^{\frac{h_1^2 + h_2^2}{2h_1^2 h_2^2} \left[x^2 - \frac{2x(h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + \left(\frac{h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]} dx \\
&= e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\frac{x_i^2}{h_1^2} + \frac{y_j^2}{h_2^2} \right] + \frac{h_1^2 + h_2^2}{2h_1^2 h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{h_1^2 + h_2^2}{2h_1^2 h_2^2} \left[x - \left(\frac{h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right) \right]^2} dx \\
&= \sqrt{2\pi \frac{h_1^2 h_2^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\frac{x_i^2}{h_1^2} + \frac{y_j^2}{h_2^2} \right] + \frac{1h_1^2 + h_2^2}{2h_1^2 h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2} \\
&= \frac{h_1 h_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} e^{-\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}}
\end{aligned}$$

Note that, we used the following result in computing the above formula

of A ,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{\frac{h_1^2 + h_2^2}{2h_1^2 h_2^2} \left[x - \left(\frac{h_2^2 x_i + h_1^2 y_j}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right) \right]^2} dx = \sqrt{2\pi \frac{h_1^2 h_2^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2}}.$$

Now to find B , let $u = \frac{x - Y_j}{h_2}$ then $x = uh_2 + Y_j$ and $dx = h_2 du$.

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned}
B &= h_2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[u^2 + \left(\frac{uh_2 + y_j - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} du \\
&= h_2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{y_j - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\frac{u^2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{h_1^2} + \frac{2uh_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2} \right]} du \\
&= h_2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{y_j - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} e^{\frac{-(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_1^2} \left[u^2 + \frac{2uh_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]} du \\
&= h_2 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{y_j - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \frac{-(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_1^2} \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]} e^{\frac{-(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_1^2} \left[u - \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right) \right]^2} du \\
&= h_2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{y_j - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{\frac{-(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_1^2} \left[u - \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right) \right]^2} du \\
&= \frac{h_1 h_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{y_j - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]} \left[\frac{h_1^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right] \\
&= \frac{h_1 h_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} \left[\frac{h_1^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right] e^{\frac{-(y_j - x_i)^2}{2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}}
\end{aligned}$$

In the above computation, we used the following fact,

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{var}(U) + (E(U))^2 &= \frac{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}}{\sqrt{2\pi h_1^2}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{\frac{-(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_1^2} \left[u - \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right) \right]^2} du \\
&= \left[\frac{h_1^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]
\end{aligned}$$

where $U \sim N\left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2}, \frac{h_1^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2}\right)$. By using the same way of obtaining B ,

we compute the value of C , which is given by

$$C = \frac{h_1 h_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} \left[\frac{h_2^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + \left(\frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right] e^{-\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}}.$$

Finally, to compute the value of D , let $u = \frac{x - X_i}{h_1}$ then $x = h_1 u + X_i$ and

$dx = h_1 du$. Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} D &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 \left(\frac{u^2 h_1^2}{h_2^2} + \frac{2u h_1 (x_i - y_j)}{h_2^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[u^2 + \left(\frac{u^2 h_1^2}{h_2^2} + \frac{2u h_1 (x_i - y_j)}{h_2^2} + \frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} \right) \right]} \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{u^4 h_1^2}{h_2^2} + \frac{2u^3 h_1 (x_i - y_j)}{h_2^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{u^3 (x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} \right) e^{-\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{2h_2^2}} e^{-\frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u^2 + \frac{2u h_1 (x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]} \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{u^4 h_1^2}{h_2^2} + \frac{2u^3 h_1 (x_i - y_j)}{h_2^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{u^2 (x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} \right) e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} + \frac{(h_2^2 + h_1^2)}{h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_1 (x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]} e^{-\frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u - \frac{h_1 (x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]^2} du \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} + \frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]} \left[\frac{h_1^2}{h_2^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^4 e^{-\frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u - \frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]^2} \right. \\
&\quad + \frac{2h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_2^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^3 e^{-\frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u - \frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]^2} \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{-\frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u - \frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]^2} \right] \\
&= e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} + \frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right]} \left[\frac{h_1^2}{h_2^2} V + \frac{2h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_2^2} L \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{h_2^2} W \right]
\end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned}
V &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^4 e^{-\frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u - \frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]^2} du \\
&= \sqrt{2\pi} \frac{h_2}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} EU^4 \\
L &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^3 e^{-\frac{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u - \frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right]^2} du \\
&= \sqrt{2\pi} \frac{h_2}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} EU^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
W &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} u^2 e^{\frac{-(h_1^2+h_2^2)}{2h_2^2} \left[u - \frac{h_1(x_i-y_j)}{h_1^2+h_2^2} \right]^2} du \\
&= \sqrt{2\pi} \frac{h_2}{\sqrt{h_1^2+h_2^2}} EU^2,
\end{aligned}$$

where $U \sim N\left(\frac{h_1(x_i-y_j)}{h_1^2+h_2^2}, \frac{h_2}{h_1^2+h_2^2}\right)$. The values of EU^2 , EU^3 and EU^4 can be obtained simply by using the moment generating function of U . For example, if $M_U(t)$ is the moment generating function of U then $EU^r = M_U^{(r)}(t)$ at $t = 0$, where $M_U^{(r)}(t)$ is the r^{th} derivation of $M_U(t)$. The simple but tedious calculations give,

$$\begin{aligned}
D &= \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}h_1}{h_2(h_1^2+h_2^2)\sqrt{h_1^2+h_2^2}} e^{\frac{-(x_i-y_j)^2}{2(h_1^2+h_2^2)}} \left(\frac{h_1^2}{h_1^2+h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_1^4(x_i-y_j)^4}{(h_1^2+h_2^2)^2} + \frac{6h_1^2h_2^2(x_i-y_j)^2}{h_1^2+h_2^2} + \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. 3h_2^4 \right) - \frac{2h_1^2(x_i-y_j)^2}{h_1^2+h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_1^2(x_i-y_j)^2}{h_1^2+h_2^2} + 3h_2^2 \right) + (x_i - y_j)^2 \left(\frac{h_1^2(x_i-y_j)^2}{h_1^2+h_2^2} + h_2^2 \right) \right).
\end{aligned}$$

We can summarize the previous computations as follows. The estimator of γ_{XY} is $\hat{\gamma}_{XY}$, which is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\gamma}_{XY} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{f}_X(x)\hat{f}_Y(x)dx \\
&= \frac{1}{8\pi n_1 n_2 h_1 h_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} [9A - 3B - 3C + D],
\end{aligned}$$

where,

$$A = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}h_1h_2}{\sqrt{h_1^2+h_2^2}} e^{\frac{-1(x_i-y_j)^2}{2(h_1^2+h_2^2)}}$$

$$B = \frac{h_1 h_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} \left[\frac{h_1^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + \left(\frac{h_2(y_j - x_i)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right] e^{-\frac{(y_j - x_i)^2}{2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}}$$

$$C = \frac{h_1 h_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} \left[\frac{h_2^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + \left(\frac{h_1(x_i - y_j)}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \right)^2 \right] e^{-\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} D = & \frac{\sqrt{2\pi} h_1}{h_2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} e^{-\frac{(x_i - y_j)^2}{2(h_1^2 + h_2^2)}} \left[\frac{h_1^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_1^4(x_i - y_j)^4}{(h_1^2 + h_2^2)^2} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. + \frac{6h_1^2 h_2^2 (x_i - y_j)^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + 3h_2^4 \right) \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{2h_1^2 (x_i - y_j)^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} \left(\frac{h_1^2 (x_i - y_j)^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + 3h_2^2 \right) \right. \\ & \left. + (x_i - y_j)^2 \left(\frac{h_1^2 (x_i - y_j)^2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2} + h_2^2 \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

2.3.2 Derivation of $\hat{\gamma}_{XX}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{YY}$

The estimator $\hat{\gamma}_{XX}$ of γ_{XX} is

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\gamma}_{XX} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\hat{f}_X(x))^2 dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{f}_X(x) \hat{f}_X(x) dx . \end{aligned}$$

The function $\hat{f}_X(x)\hat{f}_X(x)$ inside the above integral is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{f}_X(x)\hat{f}_X(x) &= \frac{1}{8\pi n_1^2 h_1^2} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \left(3 - \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \right) e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2} \right) \left(\sum_{j=1}^{n_1} \left(3 - \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 \right) e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2} \right) \\
&= \frac{1}{8\pi n_1^2 h_1^2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} \left[\left(9 - 3 \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 - 3 \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 \right) e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\gamma}_{XX} &= \frac{1}{8\pi n_1^2 h_1^2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} \left[\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} 9 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} dx \right. \\
&\quad - 3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} dx - 3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} dx \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 e^{\frac{-1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{x-x_i}{h_1} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{x-x_j}{h_1} \right)^2 \right]} dx \right]
\end{aligned}$$

Similar the computing of $\hat{\gamma}_{XY}$ in the previous subsection, we can obtain

the estimator $\hat{\gamma}_{XX}$, which is given by

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XX} = \frac{1}{8\pi n_1^2 h_1^2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} [9A' - 3B' - 3C' + D']$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned}
A' &= h_1 \sqrt{\pi} e^{\frac{-(x_i-x_j)^2}{4h_1^2}} \\
B' &= h_1 \sqrt{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{(x_j-x_i)}{2h_1} \right)^2 \right] e^{\frac{-(x_j-x_i)^2}{4h_1^2}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$C' = h_1 \sqrt{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{(x_i - x_j)}{2h_1} \right)^2 \right] e^{-\frac{(x_i - x_j)^2}{4h_1^2}}$$

and

$$D' = \sqrt{\pi} \left[\frac{3}{4} h_1 + \frac{(x_i - x_j)^4}{16h_1^3} - \frac{(x_i - x_j)^2}{4h_1} \right] e^{-\frac{(x_i - x_j)^2}{4h_1^2}}.$$

Also, by using the same technique, we can obtain the estimator $\hat{\gamma}_{YY}$ of γ_{YY} ,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\gamma}_{YY} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\hat{f}_Y(y))^2 dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{f}_Y(y) \hat{f}_Y(y) dy \\ &= \frac{1}{8\pi n_2^2 h_2^2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} [9A'' - 3B'' - 3C'' + D''] \end{aligned}$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} A'' &= h_2 \sqrt{\pi} e^{-\frac{(y_i - y_j)^2}{4h_2^2}} \\ B'' &= h_2 \sqrt{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{(y_j - y_i)}{2h_2} \right)^2 \right] e^{-\frac{(y_j - y_i)^2}{4h_2^2}} \\ C'' &= h_2 \sqrt{\pi} \left[\frac{1}{2} + \left(\frac{(y_i - y_j)}{2h_2} \right)^2 \right] e^{-\frac{(y_i - y_j)^2}{4h_2^2}} \\ D'' &= \sqrt{\pi} \left[\frac{3}{4} h_2 + \frac{(y_i - y_j)^4}{16h_2^3} - \frac{(y_i - y_j)^2}{4h_2} \right] e^{-\frac{(y_i - y_j)^2}{4h_2^2}}. \end{aligned}$$

By substituting the values of $\hat{\gamma}_{XY}$ (See Subsection, 2.4.1) and the values of $\hat{\gamma}_{XX}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{YY}$ that computed in this section back into Formula (2.1) then we obtain the first fourth-order kernel estimator $\hat{\lambda}_1$ of λ .

2.4 Another fourth-order kernel estimator of λ

In this section we used another technique to derive a second fourth-order kernel estimator for λ . The idea depends on rewriting the exact formula of λ as expected values of some functions then estimating each expected value by the mean of a corresponding function of sample observations. To illustrate this technique, let X be a random variables with probability density function $f_X(x)$ and Y be another random variable with probability density function $f_Y(x)$, then

$$E(f_Y(x)) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_Y(x) f_X(x) dx$$

and,

$$\begin{aligned} E(f_X(Y)) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(y) f_Y(y) dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x) f_Y(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

We can used the above formulas to estimate the quantity γ_{XY} that arises in the numerator of Morisita measure. That is, to estimate

$$\gamma_{XY} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x) f_Y(x) dx$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \{E(f_Y(X)) + E(f_X(Y))\},$$

we need to estimate $E f_Y(X)$ and $E f_X(Y)$. Because $E f_Y(X)$ is defined as the mean of $f_Y(X)$ then we can estimate it by the mean of $\hat{f}_Y(x_k)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n_1$. That is,

$$E(\widehat{f}_Y(X)) = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \hat{f}_Y(x_k),$$

where $\hat{f}_Y(x_k)$ is the fourth-order kernel estimator of $f_Y(\cdot)$ at a point x_k . In the same way, we can estimate $E f_X(Y)$ by the mean of $\hat{f}_X(y_k)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n_2$. That is,

$$E(\widehat{f}_X(Y)) = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \hat{f}_X(y_k)$$

where $\hat{f}_X(y_k)$ is the fourth-order kernel estimator of $f_X(\cdot)$ at a point y_k . Therefore and if $n_1 = n_2 = n$, then the estimator $\hat{\gamma}_{XY}$ of γ_{XY} is given by

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XY} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n (\hat{f}_Y(x_k) + \hat{f}_X(y_k)). \quad (2.2)$$

If $n_1 \neq n_2$ then

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XY} = \frac{(\sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \hat{f}_Y(x_k) + \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \hat{f}_X(y_k))}{(n_1 + n_2)}.$$

Now, to estimate the two quantities γ_{XX} and γ_{YY} that arise in the denominator of λ we can rewrite γ_{XX} and γ_{YY} as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_{XX} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f_X(x))^2 dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x)f_X(x) \\ &= E(f_X(X))\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_{YY} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (f_Y(y))^2 dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_Y(y)f_Y(y) dy \\ &= E(f_Y(Y)).\end{aligned}$$

So, we can estimate γ_{XX} and γ_{YY} by the mean of $\hat{f}_X(y_k)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n_1$ and the mean of $\hat{f}_Y(y_k)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n_2$ respectively. That is,

$$\hat{\gamma}_{XX} = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \hat{f}_X(x_k) \quad (2.3)$$

and

$$\hat{\gamma}_{YY} = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \hat{f}_Y(y_k) \quad (2.4)$$

Therefore, the Morisita overlapping coefficient $\lambda = \frac{2\gamma_{XY}}{\gamma_X + \gamma_Y}$ can be estimated by

$$\hat{\lambda}_2 = \frac{2\hat{\gamma}_{XY}}{\hat{\gamma}_{XX} + \hat{\gamma}_{YY}}$$

where $\hat{\gamma}_{XY}$, $\hat{\gamma}_{XX}$ and $\hat{\gamma}_{YY}$ are given by (2.2), (2.3) and (2.4) respectively.

Therefore the second proposed fourth-order kernel of λ is,

$$\hat{\lambda}_2 = \frac{\frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \hat{f}_Y(x_k) + \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \hat{f}_X(y_k)}{\frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \hat{f}_X(x_k) + \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \hat{f}_Y(y_k)}. \quad (2.5)$$

2.6 Classical kernel estimator of λ

In his master thesis, Al-Talafha (2016) derived two estimators for λ by using the classical kernel method. The first kernel estimator $\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$ that corresponds the fourth-order kernel estimator $\hat{\lambda}_1$ is

$$\hat{\lambda}_{k1} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{2}{h_1^2 + h_2^2}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} K\left(\frac{x_i - y_j}{\sqrt{h_1^2 + h_2^2}}\right)}{\left(\frac{n_2}{n_1 h_1}\right) \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_1} K\left(\frac{x_i - x_j}{\sqrt{2} h_1}\right) + \left(\frac{n_1}{n_2 h_2}\right) \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} K\left(\frac{y_i - y_j}{\sqrt{2} h_2}\right)}, \quad (2.6)$$

where $K(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-t^2/2}$ is the Gaussian kernel function. The second

kernel estimator $\hat{\lambda}_{k2}$ that corresponds the fourth-order kernel estimator $\hat{\lambda}_2$

is

$$\hat{\lambda}_{k2} = \frac{\frac{1}{n_1 n_2} \left(\frac{1}{h_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} K\left(\frac{x_k - y_j}{h_2}\right) + \frac{1}{h_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} K\left(\frac{y_k - x_i}{h_1}\right) \right)}{\frac{1}{n_1^2 h_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} K\left(\frac{x_k - x_i}{h_1}\right) + \frac{1}{n_2^2 h_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} K\left(\frac{y_k - y_j}{h_2}\right)}. \quad (2.7)$$

The above two estimators $\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$ and $\hat{\lambda}_{k2}$ are compared by Al-Talafha (2016) and showed that $\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$ performs better than $\hat{\lambda}_{k2}$ in general. Therefore, we consider $\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$ for purpose of comparison with the fourth-order kernel estimators in Chapter (4).

CHAPTER THREE

Fourth-order Kernel Estimators for Matusita Measure ρ and Weitzman Measure Δ

3.1 Introduction

Different estimators for overlapping coefficients of Matusita measure ρ and Weitzman measure Δ are proposed and derived in this chapter. The fourth-order kernel method was used for the purpose of estimation. Three new fourth-order kernel estimators for the measure ρ are proposed, which are denoted by $\hat{\rho}_1$, $\hat{\rho}_2$, and $\hat{\rho}_3$. For the measure Δ , we proposed six fourth-order kernel estimators and denote them by $\hat{\Delta}_1$, $\hat{\Delta}_2$, $\hat{\Delta}_3$, $\hat{\Delta}_4$, $\hat{\Delta}_5$ and $\hat{\Delta}_6$.

3.2 Fourth-order kernel estimator of ρ

In this section, three new fourth-order kernel estimators for ρ are derived. Let X and Y be two random variables with probability density functions $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(x)$ respectively. The overlapping Matusita measure ρ between X and Y is defined as

$$\rho = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{f_X(x)f_Y(x)} dx. \quad (3.1)$$

One possible to find the fourth-order kernel estimator of ρ is by taking directly the estimators of $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(x)$ and substitute them in the above formula. However, it becomes very difficult job to find the value of

the above integral because of the square root that arises inside of the above integral. Therefore, we suggest to use the same technique that discussed and used to estimate ρ in Section (2.5). This can be accomplished as discussed below.

Formula (3.1) can be expressed (as expected value of some functions) in different ways as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
E \left(\frac{f_Y(X)}{f_X(X)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{f_Y(x)}{f_X(x)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} f_X(x) dx \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f_Y(x)^{1/2}}{f_X(x)^{1/2}} f_X(x)^{1/2} f_X(x)^{1/2} dx \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{f_X(x) f_Y(x)} dx \\
&= \rho .
\end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned}
E \left(\frac{f_X(Y)}{f_Y(Y)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\frac{f_X(y)}{f_Y(y)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} f_Y(y) dy \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{f_X(y)^{1/2}}{f_Y(y)^{1/2}} f_Y(y)^{1/2} f_Y(y)^{1/2} dy \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{f_X(y) f_Y(y)} dy \\
&= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{f_X(x) f_Y(x)} dx \\
&= \rho
\end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} E \left[\left(\frac{f_Y(X)}{f_X(X)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{f_X(Y)}{f_Y(Y)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sqrt{f_X(x) f_Y(x)} dx \\ &= \rho. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Because the value of ρ can be written as expected value (mean) of some functions then we can estimate it by the corresponding sample mean of that function. To illustrate that, let x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n_1} and y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n_2} be two independent random samples from $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(x)$ respectively. Also, let $\hat{f}_X(x)$ and $\hat{f}_Y(x)$ be the fourth-order kernel estimators of $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(x)$ respectively, which are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_X(x) &= \frac{1}{n_1 h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} k_{(4)} \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{n_1 h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} \frac{3 - \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - x_i}{h_1} \right)^2} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{f}_Y(x) &= \frac{1}{n_2 h_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} k_{(4)} \left(\frac{x - y_i}{h_2} \right) \\ &= \frac{1}{n_2 h_2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_2} \frac{3 - \left(\frac{x - y_i}{h_2} \right)^2}{2\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{x - y_i}{h_2} \right)^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that, the fourth-order kernel function $K_{(4)}(t) = \frac{3-t^2}{2}K(t)$, where the second-order kernel function is taken to be Gaussian function, i.e.

$$K(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-t^2/2}.$$

Now, the quantity $\rho = E \left(\frac{f_Y(X)}{f_X(X)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ is estimated by the mean of

$$\left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_1)}{\hat{f}_X(x_1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_2)}{\hat{f}_X(x_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \dots, \left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_{n_1})}{\hat{f}_X(x_{n_1})} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

That is, the first fourth-order kernel estimator of ρ is,

$$\hat{\rho}_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_k)}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (3.5)$$

The second fourth-order kernel estimator $\hat{\rho}_2$ of ρ can be obtained based on (3.3) and by considering the following data transformation,

$$\left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_1)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_2)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_2)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \dots, \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_{n_2})}{\hat{f}_Y(y_{n_2})} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Because ρ can be expressed in terms of $E \left(\frac{f_X(Y)}{f_Y(Y)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, i.e. $\rho = E \left(\frac{f_X(Y)}{f_Y(Y)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$

then

$$\hat{\rho}_2 = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_k)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (3.6)$$

Finally, we can obtain the third fourth-order kernel estimator $\hat{\rho}_3$ of ρ depends on (3.4). If $n_1 = n_2 = n$ and by considering the following transformation of data,

$$\left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_1)}{\hat{f}_X(x_1)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_1)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_1)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_2)}{\hat{f}_X(x_2)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_2)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_2)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \dots, \left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_n)}{\hat{f}_X(x_n)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_n)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_n)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

then the third estimator is,

$$\hat{\rho}_3 = \frac{1}{n} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_k)}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_k)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right]. \quad (3.7)$$

If $n_1 \neq n_2$ then

$$\hat{\rho}_3 = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left(\frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_k)}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left(\frac{\hat{f}_X(y_k)}{\hat{f}_Y(y_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}}{(n_1 + n_2)},$$

where

$$\hat{f}_X(x_k) = \frac{1}{n_1 h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} k_{(4)} \left(\frac{x_k - x_i}{h_1} \right), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n_1, \quad (3.7)$$

$$\hat{f}_Y(x_k) = \frac{1}{n_2 h_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} k_{(4)} \left(\frac{x_k - y_j}{h_2} \right), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n_1, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\hat{f}_X(y_k) = \frac{1}{n_1 h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} k_{(4)} \left(\frac{y_k - x_i}{h_1} \right), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n_2 \quad (3.9)$$

and

$$\hat{f}_Y(y_k) = \frac{1}{n_2 h_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} k_{(4)} \left(\frac{y_k - y_j}{h_2} \right), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n_2 \quad (3.10)$$

3.3 Fourth-order kernel estimator of Δ

We will use the same technique that discussed in the previous section to derive different fourth-order kernel estimators for the overlapping

coefficient of Weitzman. The Weitzman overlapping coefficient Δ is defined by

$$\Delta = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_X(x), f_Y(y)\}dx. \quad (3.12)$$

This measure can be expressed in different ways as the following:

$$\begin{aligned} E\left\{\frac{\min\{f_X(X), f_Y(X)\}}{f_X(X)}\right\} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\min\{f_X(x), f_Y(x)\}}{f_X(x)} f_X(x)dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_X(x), f_Y(x)\}dx \\ &= \Delta. \end{aligned} \quad (3.13)$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} E\left\{\frac{\min\{f_X(Y), f_Y(Y)\}}{f_Y(Y)}\right\} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{\min\{f_X(y), f_Y(y)\}}{f_Y(y)} f_Y(y)dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_X(y), f_Y(y)\}dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_X(x), f_Y(x)\}dx \\ &= \Delta. \end{aligned} \quad (3.14)$$

In addition,

$$\frac{1}{2}E\left\{\frac{\min\{f_X(X), f_Y(X)\}}{f_X(X)} + \frac{\min\{f_X(Y), f_Y(Y)\}}{f_Y(Y)}\right\} = \Delta. \quad (3.15)$$

Based on the above three expressions (3.13), (3.14) and (3.15) of Δ we

can derive three new estimators for Δ . Before we proceed to estimate Δ we will show that Δ can be expressed in other ways. Consider the following well know relation:

$$\min\{u, v\} = \frac{1}{2}(u + v) - \frac{1}{2}|u - v|,$$

which gives,

$$\min\{f_X(x), f_Y(y)\} = \frac{1}{2}(f_X(x) + f_Y(x)) - \frac{1}{2}|f_X(x) - f_Y(x)|.$$

This enable us to express the formula of Δ in other different ways as the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \min\{f_X(x), f_Y(x)\} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_X(x) dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f_Y(x) dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f_X(x) - f_Y(x)| dx \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f_X(x) - f_Y(x)| dx. \end{aligned}$$

Because the integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f_X(x) - f_Y(x)| dx$ can be written as expected value of some functions in different ways then the measure Δ can be written accordingly as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E\left(\frac{|f_X(X) - f_Y(X)|}{f_X(X)}\right) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{|f_X(x) - f_Y(x)|}{f_X(x)} f_X(x) dx \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f_X(x) - f_Y(x)| dx. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\Delta = 1 - \frac{1}{2} E \left(\frac{|f_X(X) - f_Y(X)|}{f_X(X)} \right). \quad (3.16)$$

Also,

$$\begin{aligned} E \left(\frac{|f_X(Y) - f_Y(Y)|}{f_X(Y)} \right) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{|f_X(y) - f_Y(y)|}{f_X(y)} f_Y(y) dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f_X(y) - f_Y(y)| dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |f_X(x) - f_Y(x)| dx, \end{aligned}$$

which gives,

$$\Delta = 1 - \frac{1}{2} E \left(\frac{|f_X(Y) - f_Y(Y)|}{f_X(Y)} \right). \quad (3.17)$$

In addition, based on the last two versions (3.16) and (3.17) of Δ , we obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta &= 1 - \frac{1}{2} \left\{ E \left(\frac{|f_X(Y) - f_Y(Y)|}{f_X(Y)} \right) + E \left(\frac{|f_X(X) - f_Y(X)|}{f_X(X)} \right) \right\} \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{2} \{ E |1 - f_Y(Y)/f_X(Y)| + E |1 - f_Y(X)/f_X(X)| \}. \quad (3.18) \end{aligned}$$

Formulas (3.13 - 3.18) give different expressions for Δ . Each formula expresses Δ as expected value of some functions. Therefore, we can derive six new fourth-order kernel estimators for Δ that corresponds each formula.

Consider the two independent random samples x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n_1} from $f_X(x)$ and y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n_2} from $f_Y(x)$. Based on Formula (3.13), the first fourth-order kernel estimator of Δ is the mean of

$$\frac{\min\{\hat{f}_X(x_k), \hat{f}_Y(x_k)\}}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n_1.$$

That is,

$$\hat{\Delta}_1 = \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left[\frac{\min\{\hat{f}_X(x_k), \hat{f}_Y(x_k)\}}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)} \right] \quad (3.19)$$

The other proposed fourth-order kernel estimators of Δ that corresponds Formulas (3.14), (3.15), (3.16), (3.17) and (3.18) can be derived similarly to (3.19). They are –respectively- given below,

$$\hat{\Delta}_2 = \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left[\frac{\min\{\hat{f}_X(y_k), \hat{f}_Y(y_k)\}}{\hat{f}_Y(y_k)} \right] \quad (3.20)$$

$$\hat{\Delta}_3 = \frac{1}{n_1 + n_2} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left[\frac{\min\{\hat{f}_X(x_k), \hat{f}_Y(x_k)\}}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)} \right] + \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left[\frac{\min\{\hat{f}_X(y_k), \hat{f}_Y(y_k)\}}{\hat{f}_Y(y_k)} \right] \right\} \quad (3.21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Delta}_4 &= 1 - \frac{1}{2n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \frac{|\hat{f}_X(x_k) - \hat{f}_Y(x_k)|}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)} \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{2n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left| 1 - \frac{\hat{f}_Y(x_k)}{\hat{f}_X(x_k)} \right| \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{\Delta}_5 &= 1 - \frac{1}{2n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \frac{|\widehat{f}_Y(y_k) - \widehat{f}_X(y_k)|}{\widehat{f}_Y(y_k)}, \\ &= 1 - \frac{1}{2n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left| 1 - \frac{\widehat{f}_X(y_k)}{\widehat{f}_Y(y_k)} \right|\end{aligned}\quad (3.23)$$

and

$$\widehat{\Delta}_6 = 1 - \frac{1}{2(n_1 + n_2)} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left| 1 - \frac{\widehat{f}_Y(x_k)}{\widehat{f}_X(x_k)} \right| + \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left| 1 - \frac{\widehat{f}_X(y_k)}{\widehat{f}_Y(y_k)} \right| \right\} \quad (3.24)$$

The fourth-order kernel estimators $\widehat{f}_X(x_k)$, $\widehat{f}_Y(x_k)$, $\widehat{f}_X(y_k)$ and $\widehat{f}_Y(y_k)$ are given in (3.7), (3.8), (3.9) and (3.10) respectively.

3.4 Classical kernel estimators for ρ and Δ

Al-Talafha (2016) used the classical kernel method to estimate the overlapping coefficients. The classical kernel estimators of ρ is

$$\widehat{\rho}_k = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left(\frac{\widehat{f}_Y^*(x_k)}{\widehat{f}_X^*(x_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left(\frac{\widehat{f}_X^*(y_k)}{\widehat{f}_Y^*(y_k)} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (3.25)$$

and the classical kernel estimator of Δ is

$$\widehat{\Delta}_k = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{1}{n_1} \sum_{k=1}^{n_1} \left[\frac{\min\{\widehat{f}_X^*(x_k), \widehat{f}_Y^*(x_k)\}}{\widehat{f}_X^*(x_k)} \right] + \frac{1}{n_2} \sum_{k=1}^{n_2} \left[\frac{\min\{\widehat{f}_X^*(y_k), \widehat{f}_Y^*(y_k)\}}{\widehat{f}_Y^*(y_k)} \right] \right\} \quad (3.26)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}\widehat{f}_X^*(x_k) &= \frac{1}{n_1 h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} K \left(\frac{x_k - x_i}{h_1} \right), \quad , k = 1, 2, \dots, n_1, \\ \widehat{f}_Y^*(x_k) &= \frac{1}{n_2 h_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} K \left(\frac{x_k - y_j}{h_2} \right), \quad , k = 1, 2, \dots, n_1,\end{aligned}$$

$$\hat{f}_X^*(y_k) = \frac{1}{n_1 h_1} \sum_{i=1}^{n_1} K\left(\frac{y_k - x_i}{h_1}\right) \quad , k = 1, 2, \dots, n_2,$$

$$\hat{f}_Y^*(y_k) = \frac{1}{n_2 h_2} \sum_{j=1}^{n_2} K\left(\frac{y_k - y_j}{h_2}\right) \quad , k = 1, 2, \dots, n_2,$$

and

$$K(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-t^2/2}.$$

CHAPTER FOUR

Simulation Study and Results

4.1 Introduction

In this study, the nonparametric fourth-order kernel method is proposed to estimate the three overlapping coefficients Δ , ρ and λ . The asymptotic properties of this method are better than that of the classical kernel method when the two methods are used to estimate the probability density function f (see chapter one). However, the finite properties of the proposed method need to be investigated for two reasons. First, the asymptotic properties are known only when the method is used to estimate f not in estimating Δ , ρ or λ . The second reason is that the good properties of an estimator when the sample size is very large (asymptotic properties) are not necessary mean that these properties are good for small sample size. Therefore, this chapter interests in studying the finite properties of the different estimators that derived in this thesis via simulation technique. In addition, the corresponding nonparametric classical kernel estimators are considered for purpose of comparison. Finally, non of parametric estimators are addressed in this study, because these estimators are studied extensively and compared with the classical kernel estimators by Al-Talafha (2016). For estimation of overlapping coefficients, the main result of Al-Talafha was “The selection of

improper models for the data leads to unacceptable estimation results when parametric method is used. This critical limitation can be avoided by using the nonparametric classical kernel method, which gives acceptable estimation results regardless of the data distribution”.

4.2 Simulation study design

In this section, a simulation study was conducted to evaluate and compared the performances of the different estimators that developed in this thesis by using Mathematica Program Version 7. Most materials of this section are taken from simulation design of Al-Talafha (2016).

In this simulation study, the two independent random samples x_1, x_2, \dots, x_{n_1} and y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n_2} were simulated from probability density functions $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$ respectively, where the densities $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$ are taken to be the same density but with different values of parameters. The selected values of the parameters for each case are given in Table (4.1). Also, the exact values of Weitzman measure Δ for each case in Table (4.1) are represented by the shaded areas in Figure (4.1).

The formulas of $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$ that stated in Table (4.1) are:

- 1) Exponential with symbol $Exp(\theta)$:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\theta} e^{-x/\theta}, \quad x > 0, \quad \theta > 0,$$

- 2) Lomax with symbol $Lo(\theta)$:

$$f(x) = (1/\theta)(1 + x)^{-(1/\theta+1)}, \quad x > 0, \quad \theta > 0$$

3) Normal with symbol $N(\mu, \sigma^2)$:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^2}} e^{-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}}, \quad x \in \mathcal{R}, \quad \mu \in \mathcal{R} \quad \sigma^2 > 0$$

4) Weibull with symbol $W(\alpha, \beta)$:

$$f(x) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{x}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-(x/\alpha)^\beta}, \quad x > 0, \quad \alpha, \beta > 0$$

For each pair of densities, the simulated data are of size $(n_1, n_2) = (50, 50), (100, 100), (200, 200)$. One thousand replications ($Rep = 1000$) are made to compute the relative bias (RB), relative mean square error (RME) and efficiency (EFF) for each estimators. If $\hat{\tau}$ is an estimator of τ then $\hat{E}(\hat{\tau}) = \sum_{j=1}^{Reb} \hat{\tau}_{(j)} / Reb$, $\overline{MSE}(\hat{\tau}) = \sum_{j=1}^{Reb} (\hat{\tau}_{(j)} - \hat{E}(\hat{\tau}))^2 / Reb$ and

$$RB = \frac{\hat{E}(\hat{\tau}) - \tau}{\tau},$$

$$RME = \frac{\sqrt{\overline{MSE}(\hat{\tau})}}{\tau}.$$

The efficiency of $\hat{\tau}$ with respect to another estimator ($\hat{\nu}$ say) is

$$EFF = \frac{\overline{MSE}(\hat{\nu})}{\overline{MSE}(\hat{\tau})}.$$

We consider the different fourth-order kernel and classical kernel estimators of λ , Δ and ρ . The classical kernel estimators are presented for purpose of comparison. The smoothing parameter b of the classical

kernel and h of the fourth-order kernel estimators are computed by using the formulas: $b = 1.06 A n^{-1/5}$ and $h = 1.006 A n^{-1/9}$, where $A = \min\{\hat{\sigma}, \text{IQR}/1.34\}$, $\hat{\sigma}$ is the standard deviation and IQR is the interquartile range of the data.

Table (4.2) presents the *RB*, *RME* and *EFF* for the estimators $\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$ (classical kernel), $\hat{\lambda}_1$ (first fourth-order kernel) and $\hat{\lambda}_2$ (second fourth-order kernel) of λ (see Chapter 2), where the *EFF* is computed with respect to the classical kernel estimator $\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$.

Table (4.3) gives the *RB*, *RME* and *EFF* for the estimators $\hat{\Delta}_{k1}$ (classical kernel), $\hat{\Delta}_1$, $\hat{\Delta}_2$, $\hat{\Delta}_3$, $\hat{\Delta}_4$, $\hat{\Delta}_5$ and $\hat{\Delta}_6$ (fourth-order kernel estimators) of Δ (see Chapter 3), where the *EFF* is computed with respect to the classical kernel estimator $\hat{\Delta}_{k1}$.

Table (4.4) provides the *RB*, *RME* and *EFF* for the estimators $\hat{\rho}_k$ (classical kernel), $\hat{\rho}_1$, $\hat{\rho}_2$, and $\hat{\rho}_3$ (fourth-order kernel estimators) of ρ (see Chapter 3), where the *EFF* is computed with respect to the classical kernel estimator $\hat{\rho}_k$.

Table (4.1). The simulated pair distributions $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$ and the corresponding exact values of the overlapping coefficients ρ , λ and Δ (Al-Talafha, 2016).

Name of distributions	$f_X(x)$	$f_Y(y)$	λ	ρ	Δ
Case 1 Exponential	$Exp(1)$	$Exp(0.5)$	0.889	0.942	0.75
Case 2 Exponential	$Exp(4)$	$Exp(0.5)$	0.395	0.628	0.349
Case 3 Lomax	$Lo(0.2)$	$Lo(2)$	0.330	0.574	0.303
Case 4 Lomax	$Lo(0.2)$	$Lo(0.1)$	0.889	0.942	0.75
Case 5 Normal with Equal Means	$N(12, 2.25)$	$N(12, 16)$	0.722	0.810	0.559
Case 6 Normal with Equal Means	$N(20, 2.25)$	$N(20, 25)$	0.625	0.741	0.478
Case 7 Normal with Equal Variances	$N(10, 1)$	$N(10.8, 1)$	0.852	0.923	0.689
Case 8 Normal with Equal Variances	$N(11, 1)$	$N(13, 1)$	0.367	0.606	0.317
Case 9 Weibull	$W(1, 2)$	$W(1.8, 2)$	0.749	0.849	0.591
Case 10 Weibull	$W(1, 2)$	$W(3.2, 2)$	0.365	0.569	0.298
Case 11 Weibull	$W(1, 4)$	$W(1.8, 4)$	0.351	0.563	0.294
Case 12 Weibull	$W(1, 4)$	$W(1.2, 4)$	0.888	0.937	0.737

Figure (4.1). The twelve cases of OVL between two distributions $f_X(x)$ and $f_Y(y)$ as given in Table (4.1) (Al-Talafha, 2016).

Case (1)

Case (2)

Case (3)

Case (4)

Case (5)

Case (6)

Case (7)

Case (8)

Case (9)

Case (10)

Case (11)

Case (12)

4.3 Results

All computations and output of the simulation study are showed in Tables (4.2 - 4.4). Based on these output we can summarize the results as follows.

The results of Table (4.2) show that the $|RB|$ s of $\hat{\lambda}_2$ are small compared with that of the other two estimators $\hat{\lambda}_1$ and $\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$, specially when the two simulated densities are distinct (i.e. for small values of λ), see for example the results of cases 2, 3 and 8. By considering the values of *RMEs* and *EFFs* of the three estimators, it is clear that the *RMEs* that associated $\hat{\lambda}_2$ are the smallest in almost all considered cases. This demonstrates the performances of the estimator $\hat{\lambda}_2$ to be the best one.

Based on Table (4.3), it is clear that the performances of $\hat{\Delta}_4$, $\hat{\Delta}_5$ and $\hat{\Delta}_6$ are, in general, very bad. The $|RB|$ s that associated these estimators are large. This may be due to their sensitive to the values that resulted from the quantity \hat{f}_Y/\hat{f}_X or the quantity \hat{f}_X/\hat{f}_Y that arises in the formulas of these estimators. Based on the simulation results of Table (4.3), we excluded the three estimators $\hat{\Delta}_4$, $\hat{\Delta}_5$ and $\hat{\Delta}_6$ as good estimators for Δ . The performances of the other four estimators $\hat{\Delta}_{k1}$, $\hat{\Delta}_1$, $\hat{\Delta}_2$ and $\hat{\Delta}_3$ seem to be similar in most cases. This can be concluded by examining the corresponding values of *RMEs* or *EFFs* that associated each estimator of them.

The results of Table (4.4) show that the performances of the estimator $\hat{\rho}_3$ are very good in almost all cases under study. The $|RB|$ s of $\hat{\rho}_3$ are very small compared to the $|RB|$ s that associated $\hat{\rho}_1$ and $\hat{\rho}_2$. The examination of the values of EFF s that associated $\hat{\rho}_3$ in almost cases indicate that there are greater than one, which indicates that the performance of $\hat{\rho}_3$ is better than that of $\hat{\rho}_1$ based on the MSE criteria. In addition, the EFF s values of $\hat{\rho}_3$ are greater than the corresponding EFF s of $\hat{\rho}_2$ in most cases. This implies that $\hat{\rho}_3$ is better than $\hat{\rho}_2$.

Overall, it is clear that the RME s for the different estimators of λ , Δ and ρ are decrease as the sample size increase. This is a very good sign for the consistency of the different estimators, which also coincide with the asymptotic properties of the different nonparametric estimators.

Table (4.2). Relative bias, relative mean square error and efficiency of the classical and fourth order kernel estimators of λ .

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$	$\hat{\lambda}_1$	$\hat{\lambda}_2$
Case(1), $\lambda = 0.888889$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.077	-0.090	-0.040
	<i>RME</i>	0.129	0.143	0.097
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.902	1.330
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.059	-0.073	-0.025
	<i>RME</i>	0.093	0.106	0.068
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.872	1.368
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.047	-0.061	-0.015
	<i>RME</i>	0.070	0.083	0.044
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.834	1.591
Case(2), $\lambda = 0.395062$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.271	-0.308	-0.059
	<i>RME</i>	0.321	0.350	0.228
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.918	1.408
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.259	-0.301	-0.046
	<i>RME</i>	0.285	0.321	0.160
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.888	1.781
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.248	-0.294	-0.041
	<i>RME</i>	0.263	0.305	0.116
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.862	2.267
Case (3), $\lambda = 0.330579$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.752	-0.776	-0.335
	<i>RME</i>	0.761	0.784	0.397
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.971	1.917
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.765	-0.794	-0.337
	<i>RME</i>	0.769	0.797	0.366
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.965	2.101
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.760	-0.795	-0.344
	<i>RME</i>	0.762	0.796	0.360
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.957	2.117
Case(4), $\lambda = 0.888889$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.091	-0.108	-0.042
	<i>RME</i>	0.140	0.157	0.099
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.890	1.414
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.081	-0.100	-0.031
	<i>RME</i>	0.114	0.133	0.073
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.854	1.562
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.063	-0.082	-0.019
	<i>RME</i>	0.084	0.102	0.050
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.816	1.68

Continue

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$	$\hat{\lambda}_1$	$\hat{\lambda}_2$
case(5), $\lambda = 0.722274$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.030	-0.032	-0.043
	<i>RME</i>	0.106	0.106	0.119
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1	0.888
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.005	-0.008	-0.011
	<i>RME</i>	0.084	0.082	0.089
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.015	0.935
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.008	-0.011	-0.012
	<i>RME</i>	0.059	0.057	0.064
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.032	0.923
Case(6), $\lambda = 0.625187$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.033	-0.037	-0.045
	<i>RME</i>	0.140	0.139	0.153
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.005	0.912
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.020	-0.023	-0.031
	<i>RME</i>	0.099	0.095	0.111
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.043	0.888
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.012	-0.016	-0.016
	<i>RME</i>	0.075	0.072	0.079
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.036	0.935
Case (7), $\lambda = 0.852144$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.015	-0.021	-0.036
	<i>RME</i>	0.088	0.093	0.103
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.941	0.854
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.0002	-0.003	-0.014
	<i>RME</i>	0.063	0.065	0.069
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.962	0.913
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.0003	-0.002	-0.010
	<i>RME</i>	0.044	0.046	0.048
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.969	0.917
Case(8), $\lambda = 0.367879$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	0.107	0.042	0.0004
	<i>RME</i>	0.268	0.257	0.251
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.043	1.068
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.101	0.050	0.017
	<i>RME</i>	0.205	0.189	0.182
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.082	1.126
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.084	0.044	0.020
	<i>RME</i>	0.158	0.144	0.137
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.100	1.153

Continue

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\lambda}_{k1}$	$\hat{\lambda}_1$	$\hat{\lambda}_2$
case(9), $\lambda = 0.749744$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.020	-0.041	-0.048
	<i>RME</i>	0.115	0.129	0.136
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.891	0.846
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.007	-0.022	-0.025
	<i>RME</i>	0.078	0.086	0.090
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.910	0.867
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.002	-0.009	-0.010
	<i>RME</i>	0.058	0.062	0.064
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.940	0.906
Case(10), $\lambda = 0.365996$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	0.013	-0.017	-0.013
	<i>RME</i>	0.212	0.212	0.200
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.001	1.062
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.010	-0.014	-0.012
	<i>RME</i>	0.160	0.158	0.152
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.011	1.053
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.015	-0.006	-0.002
	<i>RME</i>	0.114	0.111	0.101
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.029	1.129
Case (11), $\lambda = 0.351319$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	0.078	0.023	-0.016
	<i>RME</i>	0.257	0.253	0.256
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.013	1.004
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.076	0.034	0.006
	<i>RME</i>	0.203	0.196	0.194
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.035	1.046
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.070	0.037	0.015
	<i>RME</i>	0.153	0.143	0.141
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.065	1.085
Case(12), $\lambda = 0.888693$				
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.017	-0.019	-0.033
	<i>RME</i>	0.068	0.072	0.081
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.948	0.840
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.011	-0.012	-0.022
	<i>RME</i>	0.053	0.055	0.060
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.960	0.883
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.005	-0.006	-0.012
	<i>RME</i>	0.038	0.040	0.042
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.971	0.905

Table (4.3). Relative bias, relative mean square error and efficiency of the classical and fourth order kernel estimators of Δ .

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\Delta}_{k1}$	$\hat{\Delta}_1$	$\hat{\Delta}_2$	$\hat{\Delta}_3$	$\hat{\Delta}_4$	$\hat{\Delta}_5$	$\hat{\Delta}_6$
Case(1), $\Delta = 0.75$								
(50, 50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.036	0.032	-0.043	-0.038	-0.050	0.054	0.002
	<i>RME</i>	0.113	0.116	0.119	0.117	0.135	0.106	0.106
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.970	0.950	0.965	0.836	1.060	1.062
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.031	-0.028	-0.039	-0.033	-0.040	0.032	-0.004
	<i>RME</i>	0.086	0.087	0.092	0.089	0.097	0.082	0.080
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.991	0.932	0.964	0.888	1.051	1.070
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.024	-0.023	-0.030	-0.027	-0.036	0.024	-0.006
	<i>RME</i>	0.062	0.063	0.067	0.064	0.071	0.058	0.056
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.994	0.950	0.974	0.879	1.071	1.108
Case(2), $\Delta = 0.349877$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.065	-0.019	-0.107	-0.063	-0.260	0.770	0.254
	<i>RME</i>	0.181	0.190	0.189	0.178	0.445	0.774	0.320
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.950	0.957	1.014	0.406	0.233	0.564
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.036	-0.000	-0.074	-0.037	-0.213	0.718	0.253
	<i>RME</i>	0.125	0.130	0.132	0.122	0.305	0.723	0.283
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.964	0.947	1.021	0.412	0.173	0.442
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.054	-0.029	-0.085	-0.057	-0.184	0.655	0.235
	<i>RME</i>	0.113	0.111	0.125	0.111	0.247	0.659	0.256
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.013	0.898	1.014	0.456	0.171	0.439
Case (3), $\Delta = 0.303163$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.291	-0.591	0.001	-0.295	0.835	-4.811	-1.988
	<i>RME</i>	0.333	0.615	0.215	0.337	0.838	6.267	2.840
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.542	1.550	0.990	0.398	0.053	0.117
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.237	-0.562	0.080	-0.241	0.827	-4.833	-2.003
	<i>RME</i>	0.271	0.579	0.183	0.273	0.828	5.579	2.447
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.468	1.475	0.992	0.327	0.0486	0.111
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.235	-0.551	0.064	-0.243	0.791	-4.094	-1.652
	<i>RME</i>	0.271	0.558	0.119	0.255	0.792	4.407	1.843
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.443	2.071	1.063	0.312	0.056	0.134
Case(4), $\Delta = 0.75$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.075	-0.068	-0.088	-0.078	-0.095	0.032	-0.031
	<i>RME</i>	0.131	0.129	0.143	0.136	0.157	0.095	0.109
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.015	0.914	0.968	0.838	1.382	1.205
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.041	-0.039	-0.051	-0.045	-0.061	0.033	-0.014
	<i>RME</i>	0.084	0.085	0.094	0.089	0.106	0.076	0.077
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.990	0.901	0.947	0.799	1.102	1.093
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.025	-0.026	-0.035	-0.031	-0.048	0.028	-0.010
	<i>RME</i>	0.065	0.067	0.072	0.069	0.084	0.063	0.062
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.972	0.903	0.939	0.777	1.033	1.045

Continue

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\Delta}_{k1}$	$\hat{\Delta}_1$	$\hat{\Delta}_2$	$\hat{\Delta}_3$	$\hat{\Delta}_4$	$\hat{\Delta}_5$	$\hat{\Delta}_6$
Case(5), $\Delta = 0.559819$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.011	-0.040	-0.004	-0.022	0.280	-0.020	0.130
	<i>RME</i>	0.136	0.135	0.144	0.137	0.292	0.138	0.164
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.009	0.947	0.996	0.468	0.990	0.829
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.010	-0.037	-0.002	-0.019	0.230	-0.023	0.103
	<i>RME</i>	0.094	0.099	0.097	0.096	0.249	0.099	0.135
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.951	0.969	0.982	0.379	0.951	0.700
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.001	-0.024	0.003	-0.010	0.154	-0.012	0.071
	<i>RME</i>	0.065	0.067	0.063	0.063	0.474	0.060	0.238
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.973	1.026	1.027	0.138	1.093	0.275
Case(6), $\Delta = 0.478258$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.015	-0.054	-0.002	-0.028	0.417	-0.023	0.197
	<i>RME</i>	0.136	0.138	0.146	0.136	0.413	0.143	0.221
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.987	0.932	0.997	0.318	0.952	0.615
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.024	-0.057	-0.013	-0.035	0.378	-0.037	0.170
	<i>RME</i>	0.096	0.103	0.100	0.098	0.387	0.104	0.186
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.930	0.954	0.976	0.248	0.920	0.514
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.001	-0.045	0.007	-0.019	0.315	-0.012	0.151
	<i>RME</i>	0.073	0.081	0.077	0.071	0.365	0.070	0.186
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.901	0.946	1.028	0.200	1.048	0.394
Case (7), $\Delta = 0.689157$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.018	-0.029	-0.028	-0.028	0.029	0.017	0.023
	<i>RME</i>	0.116	0.122	0.120	0.121	0.115	0.112	0.109
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.949	0.962	0.957	1.009	1.036	1.066
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.002	-0.006	-0.005	-0.006	0.020	0.020	0.020
	<i>RME</i>	0.080	0.080	0.080	0.080	0.107	0.091	0.091
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.991	0.993	0.993	0.744	0.877	0.872
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.012	-0.092	0.004	-0.044	-0.227	0.025	-0.101
	<i>RME</i>	0.062	0.063	0.061	0.060	2.466	0.068	1.228
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.993	1.023	1.035	0.025	0.912	0.051
Case(8), $\Delta = 0.317311$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	0.051	0.012	0.013	0.012	0.493	0.511	0.502
	<i>RME</i>	0.210	0.205	0.201	0.202	0.611	0.597	0.561
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.021	1.043	1.035	0.343	0.351	0.374
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.039	0.009	-0.031	-0.011	0.367	0.380	0.373
	<i>RME</i>	0.151	0.145	0.140	0.142	0.461	0.496	0.435
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.041	1.078	1.062	0.327	0.304	0.346
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.052	0.029	0.028	0.029	0.178	0.263	0.220
	<i>RME</i>	0.109	0.100	0.100	0.100	0.387	0.534	0.424
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.095	1.091	1.096	0.281	0.205	0.258

Continue

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\Delta}_{k1}$	$\hat{\Delta}_1$	$\hat{\Delta}_2$	$\hat{\Delta}_3$	$\hat{\Delta}_4$	$\hat{\Delta}_5$	$\hat{\Delta}_6$
Case(9), $\Delta = 0.590946$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.017	-0.041	-0.019	-0.030	0.161	-0.016	0.072
	<i>RME</i>	0.138	0.140	0.142	0.140	0.202	0.141	0.141
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.980	0.966	0.980	0.680	0.973	0.977
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.002	-0.024	-0.005	-0.015	0.133	-0.004	0.064
	<i>RME</i>	0.087	0.089	0.089	0.088	0.163	0.088	0.105
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.978	0.980	0.988	0.537	0.995	0.833
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.0002	-0.018	-0.002	-0.010	0.100	-0.009	0.046
	<i>RME</i>	0.066	0.067	0.066	0.066	0.120	0.069	0.076
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.971	0.994	0.995	0.547	0.952	0.856
Case(10), $\Delta = 0.298493$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	0.005	-0.028	-0.004	-0.016	0.995	0.116	0.556
	<i>RME</i>	0.202	0.193	0.222	0.204	1.007	0.283	0.580
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.049	0.913	0.990	0.201	0.715	0.349
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.025	-0.001	0.15	0.070	0.952	0.087	0.520
	<i>RME</i>	0.138	0.129	0.148	0.137	0.962	0.235	0.539
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.073	0.935	1.009	0.144	0.590	0.257
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.011	-0.010	0.001	0.004	0.846	0.045	0.446
	<i>RME</i>	0.137	0.103	0.113	0.107	0.860	0.149	0.458
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.340	1.221	1.290	0.124	0.718	0.233
Case (11), $\Delta = 0.29366$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	0.019	-0.016	-0.004	-0.010	0.996	0.163	0.580
	<i>RME</i>	0.193	0.185	0.200	0.191	1.024	0.308	0.612
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.046	0.966	1.013	0.189	0.627	0.316
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.049	0.024	0.025	0.025	0.920	0.138	0.529
	<i>RME</i>	0.163	0.154	0.163	0.157	0.954	0.226	0.555
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.062	1.002	1.037	0.171	0.721	0.294
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.025	-0.003	0.004	-0.008	0.728	0.091	0.410
	<i>RME</i>	0.107	0.108	0.106	0.105	1.187	0.152	0.624
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.954	1.015	0.986	0.091	0.705	0.172
Case(12), $\Delta = 0.737514$								
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.014	-0.025	-0.014	-0.019	0.041	0.003	0.022
	<i>RME</i>	0.101	0.103	0.105	0.103	0.115	0.102	0.101
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.981	0.957	0.973	0.874	0.991	0.997
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.018	0.011	0.019	0.015	0.060	0.024	0.042
	<i>RME</i>	0.071	0.069	0.072	0.071	0.093	0.074	0.080
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.023	0.979	1.004	0.759	0.961	0.890
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.0004	-0.006	-0.001	-0.003	0.019	0.005	0.011
	<i>RME</i>	0.057	0.058	0.058	0.058	0.072	0.057	0.059
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.983	0.984	0.986	0.791	1.006	0.964

Table (4.4). Relative bias, relative mean square error and efficiency of the classical and fourth order kernel estimators of ρ .

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\rho}_k$	$\hat{\rho}_1$	$\hat{\rho}_2$	$\hat{\rho}_3$
Case(1), $\rho = 0.942809$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.042	-0.049	-0.032	-0.015
	<i>RME</i>	0.056	0.063	0.048	0.039
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.892	1.164	1.444
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.033	-0.038	-0.025	-0.012
	<i>RME</i>	0.043	0.048	0.037	0.029
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.888	1.155	1.456
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.021	-0.025	-0.015	-0.005
	<i>RME</i>	0.028	0.032	0.023	0.018
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.893	1.203	1.537
Case(2), $\rho = 0.628$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.085	-0.130	-0.071	-0.012
	<i>RME</i>	0.139	0.161	0.132	0.153
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.863	1.055	0.912
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.064	-0.106	-0.053	0.0001
	<i>RME</i>	0.108	0.130	0.102	0.110
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.833	1.058	0.980
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.039	-0.077	-0.029	0.018
	<i>RME</i>	0.065	0.089	0.061	0.072
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.735	1.080	0.904
Case (3), $\rho = 0.57496$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	0.037	0.120	0.016	-0.162
	<i>RME</i>	0.191	0.251	0.211	0.226
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.760	0.904	0.845
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	0.100	0.153	0.031	-0.096
	<i>RME</i>	0.162	0.210	0.179	0.183
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.771	0.905	0.885
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	0.100	0.098	0.013	-0.071
	<i>RME</i>	0.145	0.183	0.153	0.165
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.792	0.948	0.879
Case(4), $\rho = 0.942809$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.056	-0.067	-0.045	-0.023
	<i>RME</i>	0.070	0.084	0.062	0.044
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.836	1.143	1.585
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.037	-0.046	-0.029	-0.012
	<i>RME</i>	0.045	0.054	0.038	0.027
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.837	1.170	1.64
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.024	-0.032	-0.018	-0.004
	<i>RME</i>	0.032	0.039	0.027	0.020
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.832	1.204	1.625

Continue

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\rho}_k$	$\hat{\rho}_1$	$\hat{\rho}_2$	$\hat{\rho}_3$
case(5), $\rho = 0.810885$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.039	-0.023	0.023	-0.070
	<i>RME</i>	0.074	0.067	0.065	0.095
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.102	1.142	0.782
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.025	0.022	-0.011	-0.044
	<i>RME</i>	0.055	0.054	0.049	0.066
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.013	1.124	0.837
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.018	-0.017	-0.026	-0.029
	<i>RME</i>	0.037	0.039	0.035	0.047
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.948	1.074	0.796
Case(6), $\rho = 0.741929$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.044	0.029	-0.024	-0.077
	<i>RME</i>	0.092	0.101	0.102	0.103
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.912	1.112	0.891
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.025	0.030	-0.009	-0.049
	<i>RME</i>	0.053	0.060	0.047	0.068
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.876	1.117	0.771
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.022	0.016	-0.008	-0.031
	<i>RME</i>	0.044	0.047	0.039	0.052
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.947	1.148	0.854
Case (7), $\rho = 0.923116$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.049	-0.042	-0.040	-0.038
	<i>RME</i>	0.068	0.063	0.062	0.063
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.088	1.113	1.086
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.025	-0.016	-0.017	-0.018
	<i>RME</i>	0.040	0.037	0.035	0.036
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.070	1.134	1.106
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.012	-0.006	-0.006	-0.007
	<i>RME</i>	0.023	0.021	0.021	0.022
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.125	1.133	1.057
Case(8), $\rho = 0.606531$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.071	-0.052	-0.045	-0.038
	<i>RME</i>	0.150	0.137	0.135	0.141
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.095	1.115	1.065
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.040	-0.018	-0.021	-0.024
	<i>RME</i>	0.099	0.094	0.090	0.096
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.055	1.099	1.034
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.042	-0.022	-0.023	-0.025
	<i>RME</i>	0.080	0.078	0.072	0.076
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.020	1.100	1.045

Continue

(n_1, n_2)		$\hat{\rho}_k$	$\hat{\rho}_1$	$\hat{\rho}_2$	$\hat{\rho}_3$
case(9), $\rho = 0.849057$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.047	-0.014	-0.036	-0.059
	<i>RME</i>	0.082	0.069	0.076	0.091
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.203	1.087	0.911
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.028	-0.002	-0.019	-0.037
	<i>RME</i>	0.054	0.048	0.050	0.059
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.122	1.079	0.911
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.018	-0.0008	-0.010	-0.021
	<i>RME</i>	0.035	0.030	0.031	0.038
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.157	1.116	0.921
Case(10), $\rho = 0.569395$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.048	-0.009	-0.030	-0.051
	<i>RME</i>	0.128	0.137	0.123	0.119
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.934	1.041	1.073
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.053	-0.024	-0.038	-0.051
	<i>RME</i>	0.102	0.104	0.097	0.097
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.984	1.052	1.055
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.026	-0.002	-0.013	-0.025
	<i>RME</i>	0.072	0.073	0.068	0.068
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.976	1.048	1.058
Case (11), $\rho = 0.563596$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.064	-0.014	-0.039	-0.063
	<i>RME</i>	0.149	0.141	0.137	0.144
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.056	1.086	1.032
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.034	0.013	-0.010	-0.034
	<i>RME</i>	0.092	0.107	0.090	0.096
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.857	1.021	0.954
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.016	0.018	0.001	-0.016
	<i>RME</i>	0.062	0.064	0.058	0.062
	<i>EFF</i>	1	0.961	1.059	0.992
Case(12), $\rho = 0.937012$					
(50,50)	<i>RB</i>	-0.034	-0.013	-0.026	-0.040
	<i>RME</i>	0.054	0.042	0.049	0.060
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.300	1.118	0.901
(100,100)	<i>RB</i>	-0.020	-0.006	-0.014	-0.022
	<i>RME</i>	0.037	0.031	0.034	0.039
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.203	1.105	0.944
(200,200)	<i>RB</i>	-0.013	-0.002	-0.008	-0.015
	<i>RME</i>	0.023	0.019	0.020	0.025
	<i>EFF</i>	1	1.208	1.149	0.919

CHAPTER FIVE

Conclusions and Suggestion for Future Works

5.1 Introduction

In this thesis, the three overlapping coefficients λ , Δ and ρ were estimated non-parametrically by using the fourth-order kernel method. In the absence of any information about the underlying parametric models of the data, the recent work of Al-Talafha (2016) demonstrated the importance and effectiveness of the nonparametric classical kernel method for estimating the three overlapping coefficients. The fourth-order kernel method is another adaptation of the classical kernel method with asymptotic properties dominate that of the classical kernel method as discussed in Chapter (1). This was the main reason to consider this method in this work. In this chapter, we give the final conclusions for this study together with some suggestions for future work.

5.2 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the simulation results that presented in chapter four, some general results can be concluded.

- 1) The fourth-order kernel method produces some reasonable estimators for the three overlapping measures λ , Δ and ρ .

- 2) Comparing the fourth-order kernel method with the classical kernel method, the estimators for λ and ρ that produces by the former one is more efficient than the estimators produces by the later one and the two method give different estimators for Δ with almost similar performance.
- 3) Based on the simulation results of Chapter (4), we recommend to use the fourth-order kernel estimators $\hat{\lambda}_2$ for Morisita measure λ , $\hat{\rho}_3$ for Matusita measure ρ and $\hat{\Delta}_1$ for Weitzman measure Δ .

5.3 Suggestions for future work

This thesis focuses on a nonparametric fourth-order kernel method to estimate the overlapping coefficients, which was compared with the classical kernel method. As another area for possible future work is to study another nonparametric methods for this purpose of estimation. Some of these nonparametric methods are listed below:

- 1) Variable kernel method (Breiman at al., 1977)
- 2) Local bandwidth kernel method (Schucany. 1989)
- 3) Transformation kernel method (Rupper and Wand, 1992)

Moreover, the semi-parametric method (Hjort and Gland, 1995 and Hjort and Jones, 1996), which combines the classical kernel method and a guess parametric model can be used to estimate the overlapping coefficients.

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